

Year-Over-Year Growth Analysis of Restaurant Sales Patterns and Visualization

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Abstract—Factors in the success of a fast food franchise involve products and marketing targeted at brand consistency, low start-up costs, franchise support, and consumer convenience (Aquino, 2023). Sales fluctuations of a restaurant depend on operational strategies and location characteristics, resulting in business failure. This study explored the sales pattern of Kenny Rogers over eight years and focused on the seasonal shift in the Trece Martires branch's financial direction. The methods applied the Microsoft Power BI Data Visualization, such as Year-Over-Year and Seasonal Analysis, to recognize patterns and contrast trends in separate years. The revenue increases every December due to consumer spending and drops every January after the holiday season. It rose yearly in three years since its first establishment and experienced a 54.93% sales drop in 2020. The profit recovered after a year and multiplied the yearly growth to 134.10% in 2022, while the sales pattern moved slowly until 2024. The researchers suggested upgrading the marketing strategy every first quarter of the year and adapting the holiday season advertising.

Keywords—Consumers, Monthly Sales, Seasonality & COVID-19

I. INTRODUCTION

Casual dining is calculated to bridge the gap between fast-food and fine dining restaurants by providing food and services to thousands of local and internal customers (Sarmiento & Apritado, 2022). People frequently go to casual restaurants to eat with friends and family, as they have put in reservation services, particularly during peak season. They provided large areas that groups can reserve for special

occasion events, and the menu is offered based on the restaurant's style. Consumers often like eating in full-service restaurants with an attractive atmosphere and high-quality services (Hae Min et al., 2023).

One of the sectors impacted by the pandemic is the restaurant and fast food chain, as it significantly increased the restaurant's already high level of market risk. The Philippine government imposed local lockdowns, affecting more than 53.3 million people (See, 2021). Analysts predict that over half of all restaurants may not survive the crisis, which presents an uncertain future picture for the industry (Severson & Yaffe-Bellany, 2020). Restaurant companies faced significant sales deficits due to a sudden drop in consumer demand and even temporarily disrupted operations (Ozili & Arun, 2020).

This study aims to assess the eight-year sales record of the Kenny Rogers Trece Martires branch. It will help the researchers determine the monthly revenue of the branch, discover seasonal shifts, and evaluate significant differences in sales performance throughout the eight years that have influenced the financial pattern of the restaurant. This study will also support the restaurant branch by examining the past sales records from the researcher's recommendations for improving future sales performance.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Consumer Behavior

The study of Balisi et. al (2023) that Kenny Rogers Roasters - Caltex South Luzon Expressway Southbound thrived during 7 years in the market industry by providing quality services that steered them to maintain a competitive advantage, increased loyal

customers, and established a brand name. Consumers are more aware and interested in the company's products and environmentally responsible business practices. Effective business strategies also helped manage internal factors such as their assets and reduce the negative effects of external factors.

An investigation revealed that the Kenny Rogers renovation at the Katipunan branch in Quezon City influenced consumer behavior by enhancing the servicescape experience, where the style and appearance of the service outlet's physical surroundings interact with customers and service providers (Roberto, 2016). The research discerned that customer satisfaction was higher after the renovation, and there was greater spending per order. The ambience was improved as the roasting party murals and celebration scenes contributed to the consumer's dining experience.

B. Marketing Strategy

Kenny Rogers Roasters' marketing strategy in the Philippines focuses on fresh, custom-made sandwiches, oven-fresh roasted chicken, and strong service. They also target health-conscious customers as they have various salads and classic healthy plates for a balanced and nutritious meal. They prioritize establishing a menu that meets customers' needs, introduces new products, and phases out the old ones. They use ingredients low in calories, cholesterol, oil, and fats for health concerns. One of the healthy products they offer is the Classic chicken sandwich since it contains whole meal bread with higher concentrations of minerals and vitamins (Bartleby, 2025).

Kenny Rogers offers items priced between 20 and 1860 pesos, ranging from the least expensive processed item, Corn Muffin, to the highest priced item, Spiced Ribs Group meal. The restaurant operates franchises in nearly all countries, located in shopping malls and independent outlets spread across many locations. Kenny Rogers runs promotions similar to advertising in TV commercials, movies, and magazines, including sales promotions, point-of-sale displays, and loyalty programs in their promotional strategies (Bartleby, 2025).

C. Market Expansion

As stated on the website of Kenny Rogers Roasters, the fast food chain, also known as KRR, dominates the industry in terms of product variety and

provides a healthier substitute for traditional fast food. The restaurant business hopes to open 100 locations within this time frame, reach 200 locations nationwide, and achieve a target sales total of ₱10 billion (Juego, 2023). The brand will have expanded to 130 outlets by the end of the year, with 10 new locations in the first half of 2023.

Fast food demand has frequently risen, leading to various product offers (Singh, 2025). Kenny Rogers Roasters aims to improve aggressively by focusing on rural regions and increasing market penetration through store innovation, since many restaurants were forced to limit their operations amid the pandemic. When customers and dining establishments sought ways to implement strict safety measures to stop the COVID-19 virus from spreading while still operating their businesses, Kenny Rogers Roasters opened its first park and ordered location and several drive-thrus.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Visualization

Data visualization is the representation of data using common graphics that display information, communicate complex data relationships, and provide evidence-based information in an easy-to-analyze format (Sharma, 2025). This study applied visualization techniques to illustrate fluctuations in sales performance using a pie chart and bar graph. The utilization of interactive dashboards facilitates a dynamic exploration of trends that allows stakeholders to assess the impact of external factors on revenue.

B. Year-Over-Year Growth Analysis

Year-over-year is a financial analysis that compares a specific performance indicator from one year to the same gauge in the previous year. This comparison acquires a more nuanced understanding of growth, decline, or stability over 12 months (Accounting Insights Team, 2025). It is useful when analyzing growth patterns and trends to view performance or market conditions. This study will use YOY analysis to identify how the Marites Branch of Kenny Rogers Roasters progressed within eight years.

C. Seasonality Analysis

Seasonality analysis is the existence of predictable variations in a data set based on a period. Companies looking to maximize their operations and

financial success should grasp the regular patterns throughout the year (CFI Team, 2023). Seasonality analysis will be administered as part of this study to recognize the occasional monthly sales performance recurring throughout the eight years. The computation of average monthly sales supports clarifying how certain months of the year account for an imbalance of annual revenue. It happens in various businesses and is forced by multiple factors, such as holidays, weather patterns, and cultural events, which can impact during these times.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: Average Monthly Contribution to Annual Sales

Seasonal patterns in the sales of Kenny Rogers Roasters are illustrated in the pie chart. December always makes the highest contribution with 14.1% income since it is the most active holiday season, during which people spend more. During holiday parties and gatherings, individuals often pamper themselves and their families by eating out during this festive season. In comparison, the lowest is April, having 6.3% due to two consecutive lockdowns in 2020 and 2021. The seasonal peak is magnificent, corresponding to the work of Parshina (2024) concerning the seasonal effects on business performance and the financial risks that expose businesses. The high proportion of annual income garnered in December should make holiday advertising campaigns and organizational preparations during this high-sales season indispensable.

Figure 2: Lowest Revenue Month

The bar graph illustrates the month with the least revenue each year from 2017 to 2024. January has been the lowest-performing month in 3 out of 8 years, particularly 2018 and 2019. It continued to decline in 2022, even with a surge of COVID-19 cases, which led to the restaurant temporarily closing for two months and resulted in a profit decline in April 2020. The data show another significant decline when the second Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) was implemented in April 2021, and dropped in the same month of 2023 without any lockdown. The results are all in the months of Quarter 1 and 2, indicating a slowdown in performance. January represents a recurring pattern with the lowest revenue across eight years, independent of external factors.

Year	Total Revenue	YOY Growth	Interpretation
2017	17,074		
2018	21,241	24.41%	Sales Increased
2019	23,481	10.55%	Sales Increased More
2020	10,584	-54.93%	Sales Decreased
2021	15,894	50.17%	Recovery Growth
2022	37,208	134.10%	Strong Recovery
2023	42,201	13.42%	Moderate Growth
2024	46,017	9.04%	Slower Growth

Figure 3: YOY Growth Rate Table with Interpretation

The table for Figure 3 shows the year-over-year (YOY) progress in 8 years, total revenue, and interpretation for each year. The total sales of the first

year of the branch are 17,074, and increased by more than two years, reaching 23,481 sales with a 10.55% gain in 2019. However, the revenue decreased in 2020, claiming 10,584 with a -54.93% difference. It slowly recovers in 2021, having 15,894 despite the second wave of lockdown in the first quarter of 2021. Strong comeback of profit in 2022, gaining 42,201, the highest sales since 2017. After the success of the latter year, 2023 had 42,201 in moderate growth, while 2024 had 46,017 sales, which is slower growth. Revenue forecasts show steady growth with periods of deceleration, particularly during crises. Yet, the direction of stabilization from 2023 to 2024 indicates that firms successfully employed adaptive responses in maintaining performance recovery after the pandemic (Bachtiar et al., 2023).

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study results show that December regularly produces the highest sales in the monthly revenue of Kenny Rogers Roasters Trece Martires branch. In contrast, the recorded lowest sales were in January, which occurred three times, but the lowest revenue month overall was in April due to the economic crisis. This difference between the rise and fall months revealed consumers' significant influence on the holiday season and summer vacation for seasonal shifts. The repeating, persistent sales in November and December, and weaker earnings after the holiday season are the repeated patterns within 12 months.

The sales performance results show that within eight years, there was a significant increase between 2017 and 2019, reaching the highest growth rate in 2018. It was interrupted in 2020 due to the pandemic, which resulted in a doubling of the growth rate. Sales improved slightly in 2021 by 50.17% despite the second wave of lockdown. The highest recovery recorded in 2022 climbed by 134.10%, surpassing all the revenue in the pre-pandemic period. There is a large difference between the profit during and after the pandemic, which steadily increased after 4 years.

The researchers suggest that the branch improve its marketing strategies every summer since sales drop in the first quarter after the holiday season. It should include menu-bundled offers similar to the healthy side dish when buying chicken, which can attract new consumers who want budget-friendly meals.

Furthermore, the Trece Martires branch should investigate a monitoring system to prevent a profit slump when sales slow down in the last two years.

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